

A Review of Sustainability in the Fashion Industry

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ABSTRACT:

One of the most polluting industries is thought to be the fashion industry. In this sector, sustainable business techniques are rarely used. A significant amount of water and other resources are needed for the production and supply of clothing and accessories. "Sustainable fashion" is one of the phrases that is frequently heard in the modern world. Sustainable fashion encompasses socially conscious brands and eco-friendly goods in addition to its goal of meeting the immediate demands of "conscious consumers." The expansion of commerce and industry has come at the expense of increased carbon emissions. Consumers have changed and grown more knowledgeable about materials and manufacturing techniques throughout time, which has led to a rise in interest in socially conscious purchases while updating their wardrobes. Sustainable and socially conscious fashion is progressively replacing fast fashion all around the world. Both new and established fashion firms are constantly updating their products to comply with the requirement and public awareness of sustainability through new business strategies, modern fashion labels, and supply chain procedures. The paper discusses evolving business of fashion, the emerging trends and the need to support slow fashion brands to promote sustainability and conscious consumerism.

Key words: Conscious Consumers, Slow Fashion, Sustainability

Introduction: As stated in the definition, "Fashion is the manifestation of a consumer's prevailing choice for garments, hues, decorations, makeovers, hairstyles, and body proportion at a given moment" 2019 (Kaiser). The production of raw materials (such as fibres, textiles, leather, and fur), the creation of fashion products, retail sales, and advertising and promotion are components of the fashion industry. There are numerous definitions of sustainability, and there is ongoing discussion over what should be sustained, lifestyles or resources? Additionally, there is dispute on how comprehensively sustainability should be defined and comprehended. "The term 'sustainability' refers to

the environmental effects of producing, using, and disposing (end of life) clothes, as well as the creation, processing, fabrication of raw materials. Despite its efforts, the fashion industry continues to be a polluting and resource-intensive across the whole garment life cycle. In contrast, consumers are becoming more conscious of sustainability issues, which is changing how they live and how much they wear fashion (Ols et al., 2017).

Research Gap

There is a lot of misunderstanding about sustainable fashion and other variables. A paradigm shift is required from establishing more awareness towards sustainable fashion practices to take an active role in making change. Splendid successes, as change do not come easy in any sector. Any change that diverges from the industry's economic projections is forbidden or at best postponed. However, a critical responsibility lies on those in the fashion industry, who had the power to create desire, must yield the power to create meaning and well-being.

Methodology: This is qualitative research and is concerned with the patterns and forms of unfolding a phenomenon. This study examines global developing trends and the idea of sustainable fashion. This study mainly relies on secondary literature, such as scholarly books, journal articles, and blog posts that describe how some fashion companies, brands, and customers are shifting toward sustainable fashion and conscious consumption.

Limitations: Qualitative research is not statistically representative. A major disadvantage of using secondary data is that it may not answer the researcher's specific research questions but will contain specific information that the researcher would like to represent via patterns and forms of variables related to the main theme. Time-wise this research data is a representation of the latest developments in the fashion industry. As this research paper is based on qualitative approach, the research does not contain any empirical data nor has any demographic data. These could be suggested areas for future research

Rationale: The research will be valuable to fashion institutes and business schools to understand the changing scenario and the trends ahead. It will serve as a guide to fashion entrepreneurs who are concerned about the environment and greater ecological integrity, social justice and be a part of the 'conscious consumerism' revolution.

This research provides background information and some emerging concepts in sustainability specifically pertaining to the fashion apparel industry; the paper also discusses the social and environmental impact, of fashion industry. The paper gives some insights into eminent fast fashion brands moving slowing towards sustainability to cater to the emerging 'conscious consumers' segment.

Literature Review:

Fashion quenches the thirst of its demand coming from consumers with at least a new "collection" every week (Stanton 2018). Global clothing consumption is 400% more than the amount consumed two decades earlier (Jia et al. 2020; Shirvani moghaddam et al. 2020). The growth in consumption dictates the amount of energy utilized in running production, the number of materials in circulation, and handling means of the materials during usage, which all seem detrimental to the environment (Chae and Hinestroza 2020; Sadeghi et al. 2021). There is an urgent need to tackle the adverse effects of the fashion industry for sustainability through circular economy approaches (Saha et al. 2021).

"Sustainability can be described as meeting the needs of the present without compromising the needs of the future" (Borowy, 2014). "The term 'sustainable fashion' is generally used in context with the production, distribution, consumption, and disposal of products, keeping in mind that the environment, animals, and humans affected by the business need to be protected" (Petrow & Leemann, 2018). According to Tischner and Charter (2001), "there are four aspects of sustainable design: repair, refine, redesign, and rethink". Walker (2007, 70) "asserts that objects can be given ideological value within the framework of sustainable development". This means we can assess products in a completely new way through environmental values. A redesigned object, for instance, can be valued according to its environmental value by applying this lens. Hence the fourth approach is the one we ought to aim for and is close to the system level innovation mentioned above. It can lead to new fashions, ways of living, and ways of doing things, as well as approaches to fulfilling consumer needs in a more sustainable way.

"Consumers in developed countries are generally aware of the environmental impacts of new industrial production and the effects of current consumption behaviour" (Wang 2010). However, "although consumers are concerned and knowledgeable about ethical consciousness in companies, this does not always translate into the same consumer choices, since consumers do not want to make ethical choices that are inconvenient them" (Niinimaki 2010). "By looking at the way consumers make their purchasing decisions, one can understand that consumer attitudes towards the environment and how they behave when buying clothing are contrary to one another" (Polianskaia 2018). "Research and realistic solutions are needed to resolve the attitude-behaviour gap, which is the biggest obstacle to sustainable fashion growth". (Niinimaki 2010).

Today there is a realization that fashion industry is built in a linear straight line, from material extraction to sale. This "take-make-waste" system maximizes consumption and passes the buck on end of life. In linear economies, raw materials are converted into products, and after their functional lives they are discarded as waste. As the impact of fast fashion enters mainstream consciousness, more and more of consumers are realizing they do not want to be a part of it. However, convenience of shopping and non-availability new trends could be a probable deterrent

Modern Day Slavery

Fast fashion has engendered a race to the bottom, pushing companies to find ever-cheaper sources of labour. That cheap labour is freely available in many of the countries where textile and garment production take place. An important observation is the phenomenal growth of women's use of labour. Women are preferred as a cheap labour force because of their obedience, low bargaining power, and easy conformity. Women and children predominate in low-wage, monotonous, low-status positions, while men in the same sector and work enjoy all the important powers and privileges. Women and children are seen as obedient workers who slip under the radar, making them easy to manage. Sofie Ovaa, global campaign coordinator of Stop Child Labour, says: "There is no supervision or social control mechanisms, no unions that can help them to bargain for better working conditions. These are very low-skilled workers without a voice, so they are easy targets." Employers get away with it because the fashion supply chain is hugely complex and it is hard for companies to control every stage of production. That makes it possible to employ children without big brands and consumers ever finding out.

A working paper by ILO Asia-Pacific Working Paper, mentions, "the male-female difference in garment sector earnings is the highest in Pakistan (64.5%), followed by India (34.6%). In comparison, the unadjusted pay gap ranges from around 17–25% in the Philippines, Thailand and Vietnam. In the Indian clothing industry, more than 38 million people are featured in a poor rural area. In December 2021, it was reported that more than 400,000 garment workers in Karnataka, India, had been receiving wages below the legal minimum at more than 1,000 factories since April 2020. Garment workers making clothes for international brands in Karnataka say their children are going hungry as factories refuse to pay the legal minimum wage in what is claimed to be the biggest wage theft to ever hit the fashion industry. The Worker Rights Consortium (WRC) estimates the total amount of unpaid wages so far to be more than £41m".

Sweatshops (typically small and unorganized manufacturing establishment engaging workers under unfair and unsanitary work conditions) in developing countries may be less regulated than in developed countries. Where working conditions are poor, the health of workers suffers from health risks such as back pain, varicose veins, asthma, miscarriage, acidity, eye strain, burns and other injuries. It has also been reported that limited toilet time causes serious kidney problems for workers, and in some countries, fatigue from working long hours (up to 16 hours a day) can increase the chances of accidents". (Mukherjee Sudeshna, 2011). "According to the Factory Act of 1948, the Shops and Facilities Act of India, workers cannot work more than 48 hours per week. But sweat-shop workers, including children, usually work 36-hour shifts when there are many orders for export abroad. They often work in unhealthy work environments without adequate drinking water and toilets". (Mukherjee Sudeshna, 2011).

A new report from the Business & Human Rights Resource Centre, Asia Floor Wage Alliance and Society for Labour & Development is recently published. This NGOs collected testimonies from 90 women in 31 factories across three major garment-producing hubs in India: Haryana, Karnataka and Tamil Nadu. The report reveals how the fashion business model, which prioritises short-term profit, combined with inadequate government regulation and damaging patriarchal norms, creates and sustains the conditions for systemic and widespread gender-based violence and harassment (GBVH) in fashion supply chains. The dominance of female

workers on factory grounds and their almost complete absence in senior management positions and their relative helplessness in the face of difficult socio-economic situations often renders them sexually vulnerable. In terms of physical and verbal abuse, sexual harassment cases are very high on clothing factory premises. Relief mechanisms of any kind exist, but their ability to provide justice to victims is truly questionable. (Mukherjee Sudeshna, 2011).

Environment Footprints

In Business Insider, Johnsen 2019 reports, "The fashion industry emits more carbon than international flights and maritime shipping combined. Here are the biggest ways it impacts the planet".

Source: www.sustainablefashion.org

According to Business Insider, "fashion production comprises 10% of total global carbon emissions, as much as the European Union. It dries up water sources and pollutes rivers and streams, while 85% of all textiles go to dumps each year. Even washing clothes releases 500 000 tons of microfibers into the ocean each year, the equivalent of 50 billion plastic bottles". The Quantis International 2018 report found that "the three main drivers of the industry's global pollution impacts are dyeing and finishing (36%), yarn preparation (28%) and fibre production (15%). Furthermore, brands use synthetic fibres like polyester, nylon and acrylic which take hundreds of years to biodegrade".

Fashion makes a sizeable contribution to climate change. McKinsey research shows that the sector was responsible for some 2.1 billion metric tons of greenhouse-gas (GHG) emissions in 2018, about 4 percent of the global total. To set that in context, the fashion industry emits about the same quantity of GHGs per year as the entire economies of France, Germany, and the United Kingdom combined. The fashion industry is responsible for 10 % of annual global carbon emissions, more than all international flights and maritime shipping combined. At this pace, the fashion industry's greenhouse gas emissions will surge more than 50 % by 2030. These are some of the 'Environmental Footprints of Fast Fashion' which are extremely scary and chilling;

- ▶ The equivalent of one garbage truck full of clothes is burned or dumped in a landfill every second (UNEP, 2018)
- ▶ Approximately 60% of all materials used by the fashion industry are made from plastic (UNEP, 2019)
- ▶ 500,000 tons of microfibers are released into the ocean each year from washing clothes - the equivalent of 50 billion plastic bottles (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017)
- ▶ The fashion industry is responsible for 8-10% of humanity's carbon emissions – more than all international flights and maritime shipping combined (UNEP, 2018). If the fashion sector continues on its current trajectory, that share of the carbon budget could jump to 26% by 2050 (Ellen MacArthur Foundation, 2017)
- ▶ Some 93 billion cubic metres of water – enough to meet the needs of five million people – is used by the fashion industry annually, contributing significantly to water scarcity in some regions (UNCTAD, 2020)
- ▶ Around 20% of industrial wastewater pollution worldwide originates from the fashion industry (WRI, 2017)

An essential part of the production process is elements such as wool, leather and fur and animal processing. Clothing and

accessories made from animal products and by-products like silk scarves and sarees, wool sweaters, fur coats, leather jackets, shoes, and belts are in demand. Every year, billions of animals suffer and die for the sake of clothing and accessories. Small animals are confined for their whole lives before being slaughtered for their fur, while birds are held down while having handfuls of feathers removed from their delicate skin. Workers who steal the wool and the skin of sheep to make shearing frequently beat and mutilate the animals. The mistreatment of goats for their cashmere and mohair is similar. The objective is to satiate the needs of the fashion industry.

Demystifying Fashion Concepts

Fast Fashion

According to the Fixing Fashion report, "Textile production contributes more to climate change than international aviation and shipping combined". Fast fashion is second - only to oil - as the world's largest polluter. 60% of fast fashion items end up in a landfill. 20% of industrial water pollution is caused by solvents and dyes used in garment manufacturing". Fast fashion is characterised as low-cost, trendy clothes that quickly responds to customer demand by stealing design cues from the catwalk or celebrity culture and putting them on the high street. Reasonable prices, immediate consumer satisfaction, corporate profits, and democratization of stylish clothing are the strengths of fast fashion. Cheap, casual clothing is produced by some fashion houses like Zara, Forever 21, H&M, and Boohoo. Zara, a major fashion brand, alone produces about 840 million pieces of clothing each year for sale in its 6,000 stores worldwide, frequently by workers whose wages are below the poverty line. Dana Thomas, author of Fashionopolis: The Price of Fast Fashion and the Future of Clothes, stated, "If your business model is based on volume, then that cannot be a part of the sustainable movement in any industry. If we are ever going to combat climate change, fast fashion will be one thing that has to change drastically." The emergence and demand for these rapid fashion fluctuations has had significant negative repercussions on the environment and society.

Slow Fashion

Slow fashion is a thoughtful, deliberate and purposeful. Slow fashion is considerate, planned, and intentional. Slow fashion is a method of making clothing that considers every link in the supply chain and tries to respect people, the environment, and animals in the process. Additionally, it entails investing extra time in the design phase to guarantee the quality of each garment. Because

slow fashion is recognized, appreciated and praised for items created with sustainable materials, high-quality techniques, ethical people management and production known for safe working environment, slow fashion items tend to be a higher price point. Also in slow fashion variety of styles and options is relatively constrained. Last but not least, the brand's newest lines and collection are not continually changing to create buzz or attention.

Circular Fashion

Instead of blindly chasing trends, the concept of 'Circular Fashion' is the idea of prolonging clothes' lifespan and creating a long-lasting relationship with them. By definition, it is about the careful designing, sourcing and production of apparels and accessories with an intention to use them responsibly in society for as long as possible. The circularity concept applies to the entire life cycle of a product: starting from textile production to clothing production, dyeing, processing, distributing, customer usage and even reprocessing and recycling options at the very end of the product's life. In an interview with Mckinsey, H&M Group's global sustainability steering and development manager Vanessa Rothschild states, "I see three main parts making up a circular ecosystem within the fashion industry: circular supply chains, circular products, and circular customer journeys" (Dec 2020)

Fig 1 :

Source : <https://www.circularcities.asia/post/>

Many brands are pushing harder on circular business models, greener materials and more sustainable technologies. One breakthrough to support these initiatives is block-chain, which is the underlying technology for digital "product passports." These have encoded information inside of them that can provide value, enhance supply chain transparency, and ensure authentication—a major advantage against copycats. Circular economy initiatives "may actually raise overall production, partially or fully offsetting [their] benefits," according to a recent study published in the *Journal of Industrial Ecology*. However, "The critiques assert that the circular economy underestimates the practical difficulties of connecting waste streams to production and of substituting secondary goods for primary goods" (Zink & Geyer, 2017).

Ethical Fashion

The V&A Museum the world's leading museum of art, design and performance has a great definition: "Ethical fashion is an umbrella term to describe ethical fashion design, production, retail, and purchasing. It covers a range of issues such as working conditions, exploitation, fair trade, sustainable production, the environment, and animal welfare". Ethical fashion is garment design, production, and distribution that focus on decreasing harm to people and the planet. In the most ideal sense, it benefits those working along the supply chain and creates a better future for everyone. Ethical fashion requires partnerships between designers, manufacturers and consumers to appropriately consider the influence and impact of manufacturing processes and consumption patterns. Outland Denim, for example, can trace their entire denim supply chain from seed to garment; they know how many farms and people are involved in producing their cotton to the wages of the workers who sew their sustainable garments.

Sustainable Fashion

According to several sustainable fashion experts, this is the most accepted definition to date: "Sustainable fashion is an all-inclusive term describing products, processes, activities, and actors (policymakers, brands, consumers) aiming to achieve a carbon-neutral fashion industry, built on equality, social justice, animal welfare, and ecological integrity" (Alves, April 2022) Sustainable fashion (also known as eco-fashion) is an all-inclusive term describing products, processes, activities, and actors (policymakers, brands,

consumers) aiming to achieve a carbon-neutral fashion industry, built on equality, social justice, animal welfare, and ecological integrity. Longevity surrounds every aspect of a forward-thinking, sustainably operating business, from its finances to its environmental features. Anna Brismar has identified seven main forms of more sustainable fashion production and consumption.

Fig 2

Source: <https://greenstrategy.se/seven-forms-of-sustainable-fashion/>

Ideally, all aspects of the figure above should be combined for every new garment produced. Hence each garment should first be manufactured on demand or custom-made (No. 1), in high quality and timeless design (No. 2), in an environmentally friendly manner (No. 3) and with consideration to various ethical aspects (No. 4). Thereafter, it should be used long and well through good care, repair and perhaps redesign (No. 5). When the product is no longer desired, it should be handed in to a second-hand shop, donated to charity or handed over to friends, relatives or perhaps a swap-shop, to prolong its active life (No. 6 and 7). When the garment is completely worn out, it should be returned to a collection point for recycling of the textile material, which can hence be reused in the manufacturing of new clothes or other textile products. Ideally, instead of buying newly produced clothes, one should consider renting, borrowing or swapping clothes (No. 6), or to buy second-hand or vintage (No. 7). Some individuals – usually younger – prefer to experiment with and renew their wardrobes often; using “Second hand (pre-loved) & Vintage”, “Repair, Redesign & Upcycle” and “Rent, Loan & Swap” would possibly be of most interest. Many individuals now prefer, “On demand” and “High quality & Timeless designs with an emotional or cultural connect” vs new mass manufactured clothes without any history with a use and throw style.

Although ethical fashion, slow fashion, and sustainable fashion each hold immense importance independently, collectively, the three are can be a unstoppable force for change

Sustainable Trends - Thrifting

Of the many trends that have risen in fashion in the past few years, thrift shopping is definitely one of the most relevant ones. Thrifting means shopping at thrift stores, flea markets, garage sales, or shops of charitable organizations in order to find affordable items. For long, thrift shopping was seen as a belittling activity that warranted mocking. Today, with conversations on eco-consciousness and accessibility, it is fast becoming a popular choice. Thrift shopping essentially keeps clothes and their components in circulation for a longer time. A larger philosophy permeates the act of thrifting as it celebrates the recycling of formerly-owned items, finding a new use for vintage goods that had been discarded, as well as the thrill of imagining what the item was like when it was new. Ms. Al Hoff published a zine called “Thrift Score” in the 1990s that celebrated this lifestyle. There are many “resale” shops that pull their more interesting items from thrift stores and sell them at higher prices. Thrifting, or buying used clothing, makes it simple to indulge in

sustainable fashion. However, as thrifting gains more and more traction, shoppers are observing an increase in retail prices. For those who purchase their clothing on the used market, this might have a significant negative impact.

Sustainable Trends - Renting

The global online clothing rental market size to be valued at USD 2.09 billion by 2025 and is expected to grow at a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 9.4% during the forecast period. Increasing online retail is the primary driving factor for this growth. Online clothing rental is a service that enables customers to rent clothes and accessories for a specific period of time. This service is beneficial for consumers looking for a designer dress for occasions such as theme parties, wedding parties, and corporate parties, and filmmaking. Moreover, this service is also suitable for individuals going through temporary changes in their physique. Rental existing garments already exists to slow down fast fashion cycles and unknown requirements for low noise in the supply chain. According to Glam Corner's Anastasia Pappas, "the rental model can massively reduce the environmental impact of a garment. By sharing a designer item with 20-30 other women who would have otherwise purchased a single item to use once and dispose of, you can help to reduce the environmental impact of such a wear by up to 95%." Major players operating in the global online clothing rental market include Rent the Runway, Poshmark, Elanic Services Private Limited, Dress & Go, GlamCorner Pvt Ltd., Envoged, Etashee, Secoo Holdings Limited, and Secret Wardrobe.

A major concern is that when fashion products are provided within rental services, sustainable outcomes are sought through intensification of use. However, intensification of use is a double-edged sword in fashion rental where increased laundering and transport of garments may in fact increase the lifecycle impact of individual garments beyond that if they were user-owned. Because this ownership model is still very new and evolving it is still not clear how it will affect the planet in the long run.

Sustainable Trends - Upcycling and Recycling

Recycling involves repurposing used clothing and accessories and may also entail turning trash into useable materials. Recycling is the traditional method of waste management in fashion. Most of us must have seen our grandmothers recycle their old sarees into making quilts or other sewing projects like curtains from them. Every product has a shelf life. But when the shelf life is extended or given a second lease to shelf life it is upcycling. To 'upcycle' is to take something already made and

then improve upon it, or turn it into a fresh item, meaning that you are not seeking out new, raw materials to start from scratch. To understand this with clarity here is an example; if we take a castoff glass bottle, liquefy it, and with the molten glass we make a lampshade, that process is recycling. If instead, we take the same bottle, clean it, and customise it as the shade of a new lamp, it is upcycling. Beyond Retro, Patagonia, Fanfare, Label Reformation are some of the major brands in this segment.

Efforts towards Sustainability

Sustainability is located in Fabindia's Core. This brand has always known its responsibility as a business model from its inception in 1960. According to John Bissella, the goal is constant development of new handmade products and content, along with fair and useful relationships with our stakeholders beholding our reputation. "Sustainability in a rural sector is an essential driver of Fabinda's strategic business model while creating means for future presence". Fabindia considers it through a project that creates a sustainable job and livelihood which encompasses an average of 60,000 artisans across the whole country. Fabindia invests in craft development and nurturing initiatives Creating opportunities and providing training, maintaining field offices for constant interaction and feedback, are all part of the investments that Fabindia makes in the sector.

Emily Chan 2019, Vogue, tried to look at the ways retailers like Zara to H&M to Asos, are working towards a more sustainable future – including cutting carbon emissions and using recycled textiles – and how effective these initiatives really were. The article mentions, Zara owner Inditex announced a new series of sustainability initiatives, including the goal for 100 percent of its cotton, linen and polyester to be sustainable by 2025. "Sustainability is a never-ending task in which everyone here at Inditex is involved," Pablo Isla, the company's executive chairman, said of the announcement. "We aspire to play a transformational role in the industry." Lowering energy and water consumption in its stores is one step that Zara is taking to reduce its use of natural resources; the brand is also working with suppliers to assess its water and energy efficiency as part of its 'Green to Wear' classification. However, it has not set a specific target to reduce carbon emissions or water consumption across its supply chain, which would be a more ambitious commitment for the company to make.

H&M is a Swedish retailer and one of the world's most recognizable fast fashion brands. It is the second largest retailer in the world after Inditex (owner of Zara) and operates in 74 countries. The company has also committed to using 100%

recycled or sustainable materials by 2030. The company is aiming to offset carbon, as well as cut greenhouse emissions, from its own operations by 40 %. It has also set a target to use 100 per cent renewable energy. Reducing carbon emissions is critical if the fashion industry wants to help combat climate change. H&M's commitment goes beyond the UN's 2018 Fashion Industry Charter of achieving net zero emissions by 2050.

Fast Retailing – the owner of Uniqlo – has committed to completely eliminate hazardous chemicals throughout its supply chain. The group discloses a list of banned chemicals on its website. Uniqlo will switch from plastic bags to paper bags in 12 countries and cut out plastic packaging on certain items. This will help eliminate around 7,800 tons of plastic a year. The benefit of banning plastic bags has already been seen on a national level in countries such as Kenya and Rwanda.

Sadly, in its July 2021 report, the not-for-profit Changing Markets Foundation highlighted that as many as 59% of all green claims by European and UK fashion brands are misleading and could be greenwashing – a tactic that seems to apply to the industry at large. The term 'greenwashing' was coined by environmentalist Jay Westervelt in 1986 which refers to deceptive advertisements or incorrect claims by companies that advocate they are doing more for the environment than they actually are. Such practices cheat customers with claims that are not backed by proofs and bear social, ethical and environmental consequences.

Conclusion

In recent years, fast fashion has gained negative popularity as an industry with significant transgressions, like high water consumption, hazardous waste discharge, an increase in human rights violations, together with bigger greenhouse gas emissions. Simon-Kucher & Partners' Global Sustainability Study 2021 revealed significant paradigm shifts in consumer views on sustainability and generational differences in willingness to pay for sustainable products and services. With the world becoming more sustainable, the call to action for companies to adapt has never been more urgent since consumers see themselves as agents of change. As conscious consumers we must penalize profit-greedy corporations using greenwashing as a marketing strategy to differentiate themselves from the competition and appeal to the socially conscious consumer using buzzwords such as "eco-friendly" and "ethical" and capture the ever-growing market. Sustainable fashion requires us, as conscious consumers, to take cognizance of these wide ranges of concerns while purchasing any product.

Creating a more sustainable fashion industry requires a multi-faceted approach. The first recommendation is for consumers to actively become more curious and intentional with their clothing purchases. Secondly, more regulation, accountability, and transparency are required in the fashion industry. Third, the media needs to bring more attention and awareness to brands that are doing good things in the fashion industry. Fourth, the consumer awareness that slow fashion though is expensive to begin with has a long timeless and classic look which can be used for many years with a feel-good factor of doing well to the planet and people.

It is high time to recognize and acknowledge the contributions of human capital especially women and children in the fashion industry. The companies need to have transparent policies where their safety is assured and needs addressed. Appropriate representation in the leadership domain, supervisory roles, and trade unions must be ensured. Brands must be legally accountable for violations of human rights and environmental compliances throughout their supply chains. A coherent movement by both consumers and brands will help build an environment which is not only environmentally friendly but also socially just, creating an ecosystem that stops exploitation of animals and factory workers. As consumers, we need to be mindful of the crucial 5 R's which include Recycle, Repair, Reduce, Reinvent and Repurpose and support brands (online and offline) which truly are making a conscious effort to make a difference.

Future Research Directions

Building upon findings of this research some directions for future research are discussed below;

1. Empirical research (with demographic data / questionnaire) could be undertaken to further elaborate emerging themes and trends in fashion.
2. A study of emerging trends in three main parts making up a circular ecosystem within the fashion Industry: i) circular supply chains, ii) circular products, and iii) circular customer journeys.
3. Encouraging research in the space of 'Digital enablers' which will make it much simpler for garments to flow through circular business models such as resale, rental, and repair.

References

- ▶ Allwood JM, Laursen SE, Malvido de Rodriguez CM, Bocken NMP (2006) Well dressed? The present and future sustainability of clothing and textiles in the United Kingdom. Institute for Manufacturing, University of Cambridge, ISBN 1-902546-52-0

- ▶ Assoune A. What Does Upcycled Clothing Mean, Retrieved Jan 12, 2022, from <https://www.panaprium.com/blogs/i/upcycled-clothing>
- ▶ Aves 2022, Sustainable Fashion – Everything You Need to Know! retrieved Nov 22, 2022 from <https://thevou.com/fashion/sustainable-fashion/>
- ▶ BoF-McKinsey State of Fashion 2022 Survey, Retrieved Jan 12, 2022, from <https://www.businessoffashion.com/>
- ▶ Borowy, I. (2013). Defining Sustainable Development for Our Common Future: A History of the World Commission on Environment and Development (Brundtland Commission) (1st ed.). Retrieved Jan 15, 2022, from Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203383797>
- ▶ Brett S. Consumer behaviour-change: The next critical phase for sustainable fashion, Retrieved Jan 15, 2022, from <https://supplycompass.com/sustainable-fashion-blog/consumer-behaviour-change-for-sustainable-fashion/>
- ▶ Brismar, A. 2015. Sustainability principles for fashion industry, Green Strategy. Retrieved Jan 20, 2022, from at: <http://www.greenstrategy.se/sustainability-principlesfor-fashion-industry-2/>
- ▶ Business and Human Rights Resource Centre, April 2022 'Unbearable harassment: The fashion industry and widespread abuse of female garment workers in Indian factories', Retrieved Jan 27, 2022, from <https://www.business-humanrights.org/en/from-us/briefings/unbearable-harassment/>
- ▶ Business Standard June 2017, India needs New Delhi-size landfills for waste by 2050: Report, Retrieved Feb 10, 2022, from https://www.business-standard.com/article/news-ians/india-needs-new-delhi-size-landfills-for-waste-by-2050-report-117062500411_1.html
- ▶ Charpail, M. (2017). Fashion's environmental impact, Retrieved Feb 15, 2022, from <https://www.sustainyourstyle.org/old-environmental-impacts>
- ▶ Chae Y, Hinesroza J (2020) Building circular economy for smart textiles, smart clothing, and future wearables. *Mater Circ Econ* 2:2. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42824-020-00002-2>, Retrieved on 9th Nov 2022
- ▶ Chen, Xuandong & Memon, Hifza & Wang, Yuanhao & Marriam, Ifra & Tebyetekerwa, Mike. (2021). Circular Economy and Sustainability of the Clothing and Textile Industry. *Materials Circular Economy*. 3. 12. 10.1007/s42824-021-00026-2. Retived on 22 Nov 2022
- ▶ Emily Chan, 2019 Is fast fashion taking a green future seriously? Retrieved Feb 15, 2022, from <https://www.vogue.fr/fashion/article/how-effective-are-fast-fashion-brands-sustainability-initiatives>
- ▶ Environmental Sustainability in the Fashion Industry. Retrieved Feb 15, 2022, from <https://www.genevaenvironmentnetwork.org/resources/updates/sustainable-fashion/>
- ▶ Falkiewicz, M. 2019. Slow Fashion Guide: Everything You Need to Know. *New Dress Code*. Retrieved Feb 15, 2022, from <https://www.newdresscode.com/stylecode/slow-fashion#what-is-slow-fashion>
- ▶ Fletcher K. Sustainable fashion and textiles: Design journeys. 1st ed. London: Earthscan; 2008.
- ▶ Fletcher, K, & Grose, L. (2012). Fashion & sustainability: design for change. London, UK: Laurence King Publishing.
- ▶ Fletcher, K. (2008). Sustainable fashion & textiles: design journeys. London: Earthscan. Gender Pay Gap in The Apparel Industry - What Needs To Change? Retrieved Jan 12, 2022, from <https://fashinza.com/textile/fashion-industry/gender-pay-gap-a-problem-in-the-apparel-industry/>
- ▶ Gillett, K. (2018). Modern-day slavery still exists in the fashion industry. Retrieved Jan 20, 2022, from <https://www.thenational.ae/lifestyle/fashion/modern-day-slavery-still-exists-in-the-fashion-industry-report-reveals-1.804605>
- ▶ Granskog A., Lee L., Magnus K., Sawers C. (2020) Survey: Consumer sentiment on sustainability in fashion. Retrieved Feb 12 2022, from <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/retail/our-insights/survey-consumer-sentiment-on-sustainability-in-fashion>

- ▶ Green Strategy. 2019. SEVEN FORMS OF SUSTAINABLE FASHION. Green Strategy. Retrieved Jan 22, 2022, from <http://www.greenstrategy.se/sustainablefashion/seven-forms-of-sustainable-fashion/>
- ▶ Hayes A. (2021) Fast Fashion <https://www.investopedia.com/terms/f/fast-fashion.asp>
- ▶ Ho Sally 2021, nearly 60% of Sustainable Fashion Claims Are Greenwashing, Report, Retrieved Feb 27, 2022, from <https://www.greenqueen.com.hk/fashion-brands-sustainability-claims-greenwashing/>
- ▶ Hornbuckle, Rosie and Goldsworthy, Kate (2020) Fixing fashion, <http://ualresearchonline.arts.ac.uk/id/eprint/16316/>
- ▶ Huynh March 2016, Assessing the gender pay gap in Asia's garment sector, ILO Asia Pacific Working Paper Series, Retrieved March 5, 2022, from https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/asia/robangkok/documents/publication/wcms_466268.pdf
- ▶ Hymann Y. (2021, April 07) Child Labour In The Fashion Industry. Good on you. Retrieved Jan 12, 2022, from <https://goodonyou.eco/child-labour/>
- ▶ Jain P. (2018), Finding treasure out of textile trash generated by garment manufacturing units in delhi/ ncr, GARI Publisher, Fashion Design, Vol. 4, Issue: 04, pp. 40-60, 2018
- ▶ Johnsen, Oct 2019, The fashion industry emits more carbon than international flights and maritime shipping combined. Here are the biggest ways it impacts the planet. <https://www.businessinsider.in/science/news/the-fashion-industry-emits-more-carbon-than-international-flights-and-maritime-shipping-combined-here-are-the-biggest-ways-it-impacts-the-planet-/articleshow/71640863.cms>
- ▶ Kaiser, S. B. (2019). Fashion and cultural studies. Bloomsbury Visual Arts.
- Katrin Bielawski, 8 Reasons Why Sustainable Fashion Matters <https://www.narahsoleigh.com/blogs/blog/8-reasons-why-sustainable-fashion-matters>
- ▶ Khandual, A. & Pradhan, S. (2019). Fashion brands and consumers approach towards sustainable fashion. In S. S. Muthu (ed.), Fast fashion, fashion brands and sustainable consumption. Textile Science and Clothing Technology Series. Springer Nature Singapore Pte Ltd
- ▶ KPMG. (2019). Sustainable fashion: A survey on global perspectives. <https://home.kpmg/cn/en/home/insights/2019/01/sustainable-fashion.html>
- ▶ Lissaman C. (2019, October 30) What is Circular Fashion? Common Objective. <https://www.commonobjective.co/article/what-is-circular-fashion>
- ▶ McCarthy, A. 2018. Are Our Clothes Doomed for the Landfill? Retrieved Jan 7, 2022, from <https://remake.world/stories/news/are-our-clothes-doomed-for-the-landfill/>
- ▶ Mckinsey & Company 2021, The State of Fashion, Retrieved Jan 2, 2022, from https://www.mckinsey.com/~/_/media/mckinsey/industries/retail/our%20insights/state%20of%20fashion/2021/the-state-of-fashion-2021-vf.pdf
- ▶ Mckinsey & Company, Fashion on climate August 26, 2020, Retrieved Jan 2, 2022, from <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/retail/our-insights/fashion-on-climate>
- ▶ Mackinsey & Company, The future of fashion: Sustainable brands and 'circular' business models, retrieved on 22nd Nov 2022 from <https://www.mckinsey.com/featured-insights/the-next-normal/fashion>
- ▶ Moulds J, Child labour in the fashion supply chain Where, why and what can be done, Retrieved Jan 12, 2022, from <https://labs.theguardian.com/unicef-child-labour/>
- ▶ Mukherjee S. (2015) Environmental and Social Impact of Fashion: Towards an Eco-friendly, Ethical Fashion, <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/72803427.pdf>

- ▶ Niinimäki, K. (2010). 'Eco-Clothing, Consumer Identity and Ideology', *Sustainable Development*, 18.
- ▶ Olsson, J., Perzon, J., Flemström, T.H., & Sjöberg, S. (2017). Trend report: Future of sustainable fashion. <https://hmfoundation.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/04/Global-Change-Award-Trend-Report-2017.pdf>
- ▶ Overeem & Theuvs 2014, Flawed Fabrics, Retrieved Feb 22 12, 2022, from <https://www.so.no.nl/flawed-fabrics/>
- Pappas A, Is Clothing Rental The Sustainable Option For Your Next Big Event? Retrieved Feb 27, 2022, from <https://goodonyou.eco/is-clothing-rental-the-sustainable-option-for-your-next-big-event/>
- ▶ Polianskaia, A. (2018). Bridging the Attitude-Behaviour Gap in Sustainable Fashion Consumption Eco Fashion Company Perspective. Ph.D. Helsinki Metropolia University of Applied Sciences.
- ▶ Quantis 2018, Measuring Fashion, Environmental Impact of the Global Apparel and Footwear Industries Study, Retrieved Jan 29, 2022, from https://quantis.com/wpcontent/uploads/2018/03/measuringfashion_globalimpactstudy_full-report_quantis_cwf_2018a.pdf
- ▶ Rauturier S. (2021) Clothing Rental Services: Everything You Need to Know About Renting Clothes
- Sadeghi B, Marfavi Y, AliAkbari R, Kowsari E, BorborAjdari F, Ramakrishna S (2021) Recent studies on recycled pet fibers: production and applications: a review. *Mater Circ Econ* 3:4. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42824-020-00014-y>, Retrieved on 9th Nov 2022
- ▶ Saha K, Dey PK, Papagiannaki E (2021) Implementing circular economy in the textile and clothing industry. *Bus Strateg Environ* 30:1497–1530. <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2670>, Retrieved on 9th Nov 2022
- ▶ Shirvanimoghaddam K, Motamed B, Ramakrishna S, Naebe M (2020) Death by waste: fashion and textile circular economy case. *Sci Total Environ* 718:137317. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.137317>, Retrieved on 9th Nov 2022
- ▶ Simon-Kucher & Partners, Global Sustainability Study 2021, Retrieved Jan 29, 2022, from https://www.simon-kucher.com/sites/default/files/studies/Simon-Kucher_Global_Sustainability_Study_2021.pdf
- ▶ Stanton Audrey. What is Slow Fashion? Retrieved Feb 15, 2022, from <https://www.thegoodtrade.com/features/what-is-slow-fashion>
- ▶ Stanton A (2018) What is fast fashion, anyway? Available from <https://www.thegoodtrade.com/features/what-is-fast-fashion>. Retrieved 11 Nov 2022
- ▶ The True Cost. 2015. Human Rights, The True Cost. Retrieved Jan 15, 2022, from <https://truecostmovie.com/learn-more/human-rights/>
- ▶ Thomas, D. (2019). *Fashionopolis: the price of fast fashion--and the future of clothes*. New York: Penguin Press.
- ▶ Timeout for fast fashion | Greenpeace, Retrieved Jan 29, 2022, from <https://storage.googleapis.com/planet4-international-stateless/2018/01/6c356f9a-fact-sheet-timeout-for-fast-fashion.pdf>
- ▶ Tischner, U. & Charter, M. 2001 'Sustainable Product Design', *Sustainable Solutions: Developing Products and Services for the Future*, Greenleaf: Sheffield, p.118-138
- ▶ Walker, M., & Mondello, M. J. (2007). Moving beyond economic impact: A closer look at the contingent valuation method. *International Journal of Sport Finance*, 2(3), 149-160.
- ▶ Wang J, et al. (2010) Potential and flux landscapes quantify the stability and robustness of budding yeast cell cycle network. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 107(18):8195-200
- ▶ Whose Time Has Come? Retrieved Jan 22, 2022, from <https://www.fibre2fashion.com/industry-article/9109/thrifting-as-sustainable-fashion-an-idea-whose-time-has-come>
- ▶ Zink & Geyer, 2017. "Circular Economy Rebound," *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, Yale University, vol. 21(3), pages 593-602, June.